

THERMAL MANAGEMENT IN FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITE APPLICATIONS

A. T. Owens
U. S. Army AMRDEC
AMSRD-AMR-WD-GA
Redstone Arsenal, AL 35898
taylor.owens1@us.army.mil

SUMMARY

Composite materials have attractive properties for many applications. In applications where thermal management is a concern, the out-of-plane conductivity presents a challenge. This work uses conventional modelling techniques to study a thermal management problem in a composite structure and evaluates potential material approaches to the problem.

Keywords: thermal management, fiber-reinforced, composites, conductivity

INTRODUCTION

In many applications, component design is driven by both structural and thermal requirements, among other things. Often, composite materials are attractive in structural applications due to their stiffness, strength, and density properties. In addition, fiber-reinforced composites have the ability to be tailored to specific applications. Fibers can be placed into the appropriate orientations to optimize structural capacity both from a strength and stiffness standpoint. Their thermal properties, however, can often lead to problems in designs where thermal management or heat dissipation is a concern. Thermoset polymers tend to have very low thermal conductivities, and even though the carbon fibers have high thermal conductivity along their lengths ($>10 \text{ W/m-}^\circ\text{C}$) [1], they have very low conductivity in the radial direction ($<2 \text{ W/m-}^\circ\text{C}$). Coupling these two materials can often lead to a laminate that has a through-thickness thermal conductivity of less than $1 \text{ W/m-}^\circ\text{C}$. These properties are well documented in the open literature [1-4].

One particular application of interest is the composite skin missile airframe. As missiles are continually pushed to more extreme capabilities, their guidance electronics are forced into smaller packaging with higher heat loads and higher power densities. The current work explores design of a fiber-reinforced guidance electronics enclosure and comments on potential material and configuration solutions. Several candidate material approaches are analyzed to determine their through-thickness conductivity and comments are made about planned experimental approaches to evaluate the material solutions.

PRELIMIINARY MODELING

A finite element model was created to establish an understanding of the problem at hand. Using this model, a trade study was performed to assess the effect of thermal conductivity on the thermal response within the structure.

Modeling Approach

ABAQUS Finite Element software was used to build a simple heat transfer model of a system. The system consists of a 17.8 cm diameter cylinder of length 40.6 cm and thickness of 2.3 mm. A plate is mounted within the cylinder to represent a circuit board with two areas for the application of heat loads. A heat spreader plate is inserted to carry the heat from the circuit board to the interior wall of the cylinder. An arbitrary heat load of 50 Watts is applied to the circuit board and the analysis is run for a time step of 15 minutes. The temperatures are monitored at the location of the heat load. The baseline model assumes the outer skin of the cylinder is constructed from aluminum. Then successive models are run assuming the outer skin of the cylinder is constructed from a fiber-reinforced composite material. The through-thickness conductivity (k_3) of the composite is modified for each successive model to quantify the effect on the thermal response at the heat load. Internal and external convective boundary conditions are placed on the model. The material properties and boundary conditions are listed in Tables 1 and 2.

Figure 1: Finite element model geometry and mesh

Table 1: Boundary conditions

	Coefficient	Reference Temperature
External Convection	10 W/m ² K	71 °C
Internal Convection	0.1 W/m ² K	100 °C

Table 2: Assumed material properties

	Specific Heat	Density	Conductivity
Aluminum	896 J/(kg-°C)	2700 kg/m ³	167 W/(m-°C)
Composite	1000 J/(kg-°C)	1500 kg/m ³	0.2-200 W/(m-°C)

Results

For the first set of models, k_3 was changed in successive models. The in-plane conductivities (k_1 and k_2) were held constant at 3 W/(m-°C). Figure 3 demonstrates the effect of the change in k_3 conductivities on the overall thermal response. There is a notable increase in temperature at the internal heat source with the introduction of the composite skin. Large increases in k_3 decrease the overall internal temperature; however, increasing the conductivity several orders of magnitude only decreases the internal temperature marginally.

Figure 2: Typical temperature distributions

Figure 3: Temperature histories for various k_3 values

With the sole effect of k_3 on overall thermal response established, the in-plane thermal conductivities, k_1 and k_2 , were modified. Two scenarios were analyzed. The first scenario involved a k_3 value of 20 W/(m-°C) with an increased in-plane conductivity 10 W/(m-°C). The second scenario involved the same as the first along with the introduction of a high conductivity, 400 W/(m-°C) heat spreader lining the interior surface. Increasing the conductivity of the spreader or the in-plane conductivity of the composite has a drastic improvement in overall system response. The results are quantified in Fig. 4. This demonstrates that thermal management in composite structures will likely require a material solution as well as a configuration solution.

Figure 4: Temperature histories for various configurations

The goal is to provide the missile designer with a toolbox of options in terms of structural and thermal tradeoffs. Based on these results, it may be possible to achieve this goal by integrating a limited amount of high conductivity material through the thickness along with integrating a high conductivity material such as pitch carbon fibers or pyrolytic graphite on the inner surface of the laminate to act as a heat spreading mechanism. In the following models, more detail regarding the effects of a high conductivity heat spreader were explored. A range of spreader areas and thicknesses were evaluated.

For this set of models, the in plane conductivities for the composite skin were held constant at $3 \text{ W}/(\text{m}\cdot^\circ\text{C})$ and the out of plane conductivity was held constant at $20 \text{ W}/(\text{m}\cdot^\circ\text{C})$, with the exception of the bare carbon model used to establish the upper bound. This bound was established with a through-thickness conductivity of $0.1 \text{ W}/(\text{m}\cdot^\circ\text{C})$. A high conductivity inner layer was established on the composite with a nominal isotropic conductivity of $400 \text{ W}/(\text{m}\cdot^\circ\text{C})$. As shown in Fig. 5, the amount of area covered was varied from 12.5% to 75%. The thickness of the heat spreader region was held constant at 1 mm. Introducing the increase in surface area exposure of the skin of the airframe has a drastic improvement in overall thermal response even for a carbon epoxy structure with a marginal increase in through-thickness conductivity.

Figure 5: Temperature histories for various % area

Next, this model was modified to see the effect of the thickness of the heat spreader. The area was held constant at 25% covered area and the thickness was varied from 0.5 mm to 3 mm. The same aluminum and bare carbon models were used to establish lower and upper bounds of the thermal performance.

Figure 6: Temperature histories for various spreader thicknesses

In summary, these models demonstrate the overall effect of the various approaches to the thermal management problem in a composite skin missile airframe. It will be necessary to integrate higher through-thickness conductivity into the airframe in order to achieve the time response necessary to successfully move heat out of the structure. However, increasing the through-thickness conductivity several orders of magnitude may prove to be very difficult from a materials standpoint and unnecessary from a thermal systems standpoint. Achieving a through-thickness conductivity of 20 W/m-°C could potentially provide drastic improvement to the thermal management problem.

RELATED WORK

In terms of studying the material component to the solution, several material candidates have been identified. For example, braided pitch-based carbon fibers have been shown to potentially improve thermal conductivity in carbon fiber-reinforced structures [5]. Exfoliated graphite has also demonstrated drastic improvements in matrix thermal conductivity [6]. In addition, through-thickness pins have high potential for performance based on rule-of-mixtures calculations. Each of these approaches has its own advantages and disadvantages. For through-thickness pins, the effective conductivity can be calculated using rule of mixtures (Fig. 7):

$$\lambda_{EFF} = V_1\lambda_1 + V_2\lambda_2$$

Figure 7: Rule of mixtures thermal conductivity for various fillers

Most of these approaches will require a certain level of research and development to bring them to maturity. However they show great promise in terms of their potential ability to solve the heat transfer problem in carbon fiber-reinforced applications.

A current effort is underway to study many of these material solution approaches at the coupon level. Samples are being fabricated with various through-thickness filler configurations and the coupons will be tested. For this testing, the comparative rod method [7] will be used. In addition, results will be compared with results from some transient plane source method tests [8] as well as laser flash apparatus method tests [9].

FUTURE WORK AND CONCLUSIONS

The intent of the current modelling effort is simply to gain insight into the thermal management problem and to determine the most appropriate ways to solve the problem. In parallel with the current material testing program, the finite element heat transfer models will be refined to include more packaging detail as well as more realistic boundary conditions. With the higher fidelity models, the system thermal performance will be evaluated for the various material candidates. Once the various approaches are better understood at the coupon level and the level of understanding of fabrication is improved, laboratory-level hardware will be fabricated to validate these models as well as compare the candidates at the system level. Fabricating larger scale, representative parts will also serve to demonstrate manufacturing feasibility at the system level.

The proposed test setup will include a carbon-epoxy cylinder with various materials integrated through the thickness. The cylinder will be fitted with end caps to prevent forced convection on any of the interior surfaces. Thermocouples will be mounted on the external surface of the cylinder as well as on the internal surface near the heat source. The thermocouples will be placed in an array to take advantage of symmetry but still capture the overall heat distributions in the part. A known heat load will be applied to the spreader and the temperature distribution will be monitored. The main

intent of the testing will be to identify which candidate best minimizes the insulative effects of the carbon-epoxy structure. All of the results will be compared against a baseline aluminum structure.

Figure 8: Test cylinder configuration

Figure 9: Thermocouple locations

The composite skin missile airframe designer has many challenges in terms of thermal management. As electronics packages are driven to smaller sizes and more stringent requirements, it will be imperative that options exist for evacuating heat from a composite structure. There are several promising approaches to solve this problem. The current effort will continue to study each of these options and improve understanding of the effects of each option on system thermal performance.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author would like to acknowledge the support of the Applied Smaller Lighter Cheaper Munitions Systems Army Technology Objective (ASLCMS-ATO) Program Manager, Susan Dunbar and Deputy Program Manager, Paige Walker . Without their support this work would not be possible.

References

1. Kutz, M. *Handbook of Materials Selection*, 2002, 365-368.
2. Springer, G. S., and Tsai, S. W., "Thermal conductivities of unidirectional materials," *Journal of Composite Materials*, V. 1, No. 2, 1967, 166-173.
3. Rolfes, R., and Hammerschmidt, U., "Transverse thermal conductivity of CFRP laminates: A numerical and experimental validation of approximation formulae," *Composites Science and Technology*, 54, 1995, 45-54.
4. Pilling, M. W., Yates, B., Black, M. A., Tattersall, P. "The thermal conductivity of carbon fibre-reinforced composites," *Journal of Materials Science*, 14, 1979, 1326-1338.
5. Sharp, K., Bogdanovich, A. E., Tang, W., Heider, D., Advani, S., and Glowiana, M, "High through-thickness thermal conductivity composites based on three-dimensional woven fiber architectures," *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 46, No. 11, 2008, 2944-2954.
6. Ganguli, S., Roy, A. K., and Anderson, D. P., "Improved thermal conductivity for chemically functionalized exfoliated graphite/epoxy composites," *Carbon*, 46, 2008, 806-817.
7. Standard Test Method for Thermal Conductivity of Solids by Means of the Guarded-Comparative-Longitudinal Heat Flow Technique, ASTM E 1225.
8. Plastics – Determination of thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity – Part 2: Transient plane heat source (hot disc) method, ISO 22007-2:2008.
9. Standard Test Method for Thermal Diffusivity by the Flash Method, ASTM E 1461.